

Assessing Dual Dimensions of Machine Learning Adoption in Libraries

Onwubiko Emmanuel Chidiadi (PhD)

Michael Okpara University of Ariculture, Umudike, Nigeria
ORCID: 0000-0001-9386-4972
onwubikoemma@yahoo.com or emmabikos@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

As a subset of artificial intelligence (AI), machine learning automatically enables a system to learn and improve from experience. This paper focuses on the two facets of the adoption of machine learning in libraries on library services. The study utilized a qualitative research approach and in so doing, the researcher adopted a systematic review of literature which helped in gathering data in line with the purpose of the study. Going by the reviewed literature, the first facet as identified, is that machine learning has the potential to enhancing access to information in libraries while the second facet, exposes the dangers associated with the adoption of machine learning in any library especially in the areas of technological growth and inclusivity in accessibility differences. In all, the emphasis is that libraries and librarians ought to adopt and lean on the associated gains of machine learning to harness its potentialities in libraries. The paper is of the opinion that libraries should come up with continual training and support to librarians and library users, libraries should partner stakeholders in digitization and related fields on comprehensive machine adoption in digital libraries and every other desirable information centres such as galleries and museums.

.Keywords: Machine Learning, Machine Learning Algorithms, Librarian. Library Services, Artificial Intelligence, Digital Libraries

1. INTRODUCTION

As the world goes round, man on daily basis encounters changes as a result of scientific and technological breakthroughs geared towards bettering his life. In this era, the technological breakthrough that has remained so prominent, is the emergence of information and communication technology (ICT) with it associated exponential growth in information masterminded by the invention of the famous information superhighway – the internet that led to information explosion and overload. As professionals, librarians are the most hit of this development, knowing that not all information should be chewed, swallowed and digested therefore, there are needs to apply every technological antennary to select, acquire and disseminate the right form of information as to effectively and efficiently satisfy the information needs of their teeming clientele. To this end, one thought in the mind of every librarian is; how to satisfy the information needs of library users and the most suitable technology to achieve this.

The emphasis is that in the past two decades, the globe has undoubtedly experienced man's greatest inventions in ICT with the emergence of avatar, blockchain technology, metaverse and artificial intelligence/robotics and the subset, machine learning among others. In all, they are powered by the computer, while in recent time, all attention has shifted to the Artificial Intelligence (AI) to which machine learning is a part.

Machine learning which is an offshoot of the artificial intelligence, automatically empowers a machine or system to learn and work based on experience garnered. Instead of explicit programming, machine learning uses algorithms to analyze large amounts of data, learn from the insights and then make a logical conclusion (Muhammad, Jamal, Diaz-Martinez, et al., 2022). It is therefore, that aspect of in artificial intelligence involved with the development and study of statistical algorithms which learn from data and relate same to unseen data and with this, performs designed tasks without being programmed. Machine learning algorithms on their own are models that are from inception designed for computations that allow computers to master patterns from which predictions or decisions are made based on data without any laydown instruction. These algorithms are necessity to contemporary artificial intelligence and are presently utilized in various applications such as; image and speech recognition, natural language processing, recommendation systems, fraud detection and autonomous vehicles (Abhay, Bhadani and Dhanya, 2016). This implies that machine learning algorithms are essentially sets of instructions that allow computers to learn from data, make predictions and improve their performance over time.

In generality, artificial intelligence (AI) is wide field of study that focuses on the utilization of technologies especially information communication technologies, to build machines and computers that have the ability to replicate human intelligence more so in the ways of human knowledge and understanding. The emphasis being on the areas of being able to virtualize, comprehend, respond accordingly to both spoken and written language, systematically break down data as well as being able to take decisions and make suggestions among others (Ahmed, Sarker and Chiang, 2016). All the same, artificial intelligence as presumed by many, is not a standalone system rather, a set of technologies inculcated into a system so that it could logically think, learn and perform to solving a complex problem.

In common usage, the terms "machine learning" and "artificial intelligence" are often used interchangeably due to the prevalence of machine learning for AI purposes in contemporary digital ecosystem. But, the two terms in meanings are quite different. While AI refers to the general attempt to create machines that have the ability to reason and perform like the humans, machine learning specifically refers to the use of machine learning algorithms and data sets to do so. One helpful way to remember the difference between machine learning and artificial intelligence explained Google Cloud is to imagine them as umbrella categories. Artificial intelligence is the overarching term that covers a wide variety of specific approaches and algorithms while machine learning sits under that umbrella, but so do other major subfields, such as deep learning, robotics, expert systems, and natural language processing (Mohamed, Ali, et. al., 2022).

Ultimately, it is believed that the application of machine learning in library services will go a long way to hastening effective and efficient service delivery. This is built on the premise that Artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) have become major facilitator in reshaping our world and the way we think, act and make decisions (Das and Islam, 2021) The irony of it is that in recent time the digital global ecosystem is almost ruled by AI and its branches. In this regard, various functionalities of machine learning and artificial intelligence in general, have been adopted by world leading organizations such as Google, IBM, Amazon, Netflix, Expedia, Meta and so many others with a view to improving their products and services. Above all, majority of principal sectors in national development in developed nations and few developing nations such as health, education, weather, agriculture, business, government and stock, non-government agencies have either adopted or are showing interest in the adoption and utilization of these technologies as to simplify and neutralize workload, enhance and facilitate optimal productivity, reduce human interaction and most importantly lead the digital-world in a smart and sophisticated way and libraries especially those of the developed nations are known to be adopting some of these fascinating contemporary technologies which ML is one, with the purpose of ensuring that all their library users' information needs are satisfied (Das and Islam, 2021).

Suffice to say, as king of information management and dissemination as well as custodians of knowledge, libraries like other institutions and bodies, are also embracing most if not all emerging information technologies into their modus operandi. This is as a result of daily astronomical growth in information and volumes of data being created on daily basis, otherwise called big data as well as the time required to process and make these data handy for the final consumers who are the library users that ever desiring that libraries and librarians should satisfy their information needs. As has also been noted, the advancement in computer processing speed and capacity as well as the popularity of using the networked environment for data processing among others, are some of the major potential combinations that create the possibility to mining real-time data and deliver information outputs accordingly (Johnson, Adams et. al., 2015). The emphasis is that, application of ML is an aid for effective interaction among smart technologies which will in turn enhance the efficiency of various libraries that have eventually shifted from the orthodox library services to intelligent library systems, through revolving users' needs and providing customized and all times knowledge services.

The implication is that, the application of ML technology provides automated solutions for the acquisition of novel knowledge which is a sine-qua-non for the development of a full intelligent library which will stand the test of time, place or location. The aversion is that the emergence of ML and its source the AI, has created a new horizon in revolutionizing both technical and user services in libraries. Ultimately ML is known to have these self-learning and self-doing abilities that can help libraries carryout functional interaction among machine-automated intelligent technologies for high efficiency and co-creation of all library services (Das and Islam, 2021).

It is in view of the above that this paper intend to take review of areas machine learning are workable in libraries, accrued benefits and likely constraints to its application for effective and efficient service delivery as to providing answer to the question: as to whether the integration of ML in libraries in Nigeria is a catholicon or a nightmare to efficient library service delivery?. This study has become necessary

in this part of the globe, as there are dearth of literature and inadequate knowledge in the field and the study therefore, is one of the ways to close the gap and create the desired awareness among libraries, librarians and the general public that the library is designated to serve.

1.1. Objectives of the study

The specific objectives of the study therefore are to:

1. Determine services ML can be used for in libraries
2. Examine the benefits of utilizing ML in libraries
3. Find out the dangers posed by using ML in libraries

2. METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a qualitative research method, using the explanatory research approach to examine the need for libraries to utilize ML technology in this digital ecosystem. A step-by-step review of related literature was carried out in the cause of the study, with special consideration on the nature of topic under study, the researcher did utilize different search engines, databases such as Google search, Microsoft edge, AcademiaEdu, ResearchGate and other useful websites with a view to obtaining both retrospective on current literature on the topic. The search strategy involved the use of key terms such as "libraries and ML " and "Use of ML in libraries." This methodological approach lasted for a period of three weeks within which, relevant articles and literature were gathered. With the compilation of articles and other literature from the databases, search engines and websites, the researchers meticulously examined and assimilated the content as they relate to the need for libraries to adopt ML and the associated dangers into the paper. The entire research project was took over four months to be completed, with a high level of commitment to rigorous investigation. Ethical considerations were also meticulously observed throughout the research process, with proper referencing of authors cited in the paper and ensuring that the presentation of the findings was consistent.

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

3.1. MACHINE LEARNING (ML) AS A CONCEPT

The development of machine learning as an offshoot of artificial intelligence (AI) could be traced to 1959, when Arthur Samuel came up with the idea of machine learning without being clearly instructed on any task to be performed. The whole idea was based on the lecture of Alan Turing at the London Mathematical Society in February 20, 1947 where he posit, the need for such a machine with the ability to learn from experiences. In this regard, he defined Machine learning as a "field of study that gives computers the ability to learn without being clearly instructed on the task to be performed. However, it is on record, that among the world premier successful self-learning programs was the Samuel

Checkers-Playing Program and this formed the early demonstration of the fundamental concept of AI (Wiederhold, McCarthy and Feigenbaum, 1990).

Generally, the term machine learning in the contemporary global digital ecosystem, has been given face-lift definitions with each of the definitions agreeing on one fact and that is that ML involves machine learning from data. On this ground Ex Libris Whitepaper (2020), stipulates that the whole idea of the technology involves the act in which machines after learning from experience from dataset create its own classification thereby surprisingly fastening the recognition of the statistical patterns. While from the layman's point of view, the explanation is that, machine learning involves using computers (i.e., machines) to identify patterns within large amounts of data (Ayyadevara, 2018). As the name denotes, machine learning implies that, over time as experience accrues as a result of a larger sample of data analyzed, the computer will become better at performing analytical tasks. However, what makes machine learning possible are learning series of mathematical steps designed for computer instructions which gives answers to specific questions or solution to a particular question (algorithms), which facilitate one of the two principle learning model approaches. The two approaches being, supervised and unsupervised or non-supervised learning model (Ayyadevara, 2018; Fernandez, 2016).

Professionally, machine learning (ML) is described as field of study in artificial intelligence concerned with the development and study of statistical sets of mathematical steps (statistical algorithms) with the ability to learn from data and generalize to unseen data and thus perform tasks without clearly stated instructions (IBM, 2021). It pertinent to state that there is a sub-discipline in machine learning called the deep learning and the recorded advances in this sub, has given way to a class of statistical algorithms known as neural network, to exceed the performance of past machine learning approaches. Furtherance definition is that ML, is that aspect of AI that automatically enables a machine or system to learn and improve from experience (Google Cloud, 2024). Ultimately, ML utilizes algorithms analyze large amounts of data, learn from the insights, afterwards make informed decisions rather than relying on of clearly state instruction or explicit programming. Whereas to Coursera (2025), machine learning is a subfield of artificial intelligence that utilizes algorithms trained on data sets to create models capable of performing tasks that only humans would have performed, such as categorizing images, analyzing data or predicting price fluctuations. Today, machine learning is one of the most common forms of artificial intelligence and is known to be powering many of the digital goods and services that are daily use. In nutshell, ML is an application of AI that allows machines to extract knowledge from data and learn from it autonomously.

The assertion is that machine learning has now been considered as a game-changer through providing solutions to complex real-world conundrum in a sizable way beneficiary with a wide range of computing tasks. It is not only revolutionizing the way things are done, it is typically the most mainstream type of AI technology presently in use. Machine learning is said to be constantly changing sometimes with data mining in that machine learning concentrates on prediction on the basis of known properties that are learned from the training data while data mining on the other hand, focuses on the discovery of unknown properties in the data. From the definitions, one can deduce that machine learning is a common type of artificial intelligence that operates based on studied data.

Source: Miro Medium (2024)

https://miro.medium.com/v2/resize:fit:710/1*kiddi9eq0gcf9aojx3z8cqq.jpeg

Writing on how ML works, Coursera (2025), explains that at central part of it is that the method simply utilizes series of mathematical steps that help it to draw conclusion or provide answer to a particular question or problem, more so, lists of adjustable rules that can also be refined using past data sets to make predictions and divide them into sets (categorization) when confronted with new data. Buttressing the point on how ML works, a machine learning algorithm may be “trained” on a data set consisting of thousands of images of flowers that are labeled with each of their different flower types so as to correctly identify a flower in a new photograph based on the differentiating characteristics it learned from other pictures. The identification of same flower type but in a different scenario will be based on the past experienced not because of any explicit programming. The bottom line is that, the strength of ML as well as AI depends on that the machines have ability recognize patterns efficiently and in an organized process as well as at a scale and velocity that humans cannot imagine or get closer to.

3.1.1. MACHINE LEARNING ALGORITHMS

As noted overleaf, the operations of machine learning is based on studied statistical algorithms or what Samuel Arthur tagged not being explicitly programmed which are known as machine learning algorithms. Machine learning algorithms are computational models that enable computers to understand patterns and make predictions or decisions based on data without explicit programming or defined instruction. These algorithms are fundamental to modern artificial intelligence as they are being utilized in many applications, including image and speech recognition, natural language processing and recommendation systems as well as in fraud detection and autonomous vehicles (Ayyadevara, 2018). These algorithms can be described simply as, step-by-step instructions that allow a computer to solve a particular type of learning problem.

Figure 2: Machine Learning Algorithms

Source: Geeks for Geeks (2024). <https://www.geeksforgeeks.org/machine-learning-algorithms>

The emphasis is that machine learning algorithms are so desirable sets of instructions that allow computers to learn from data, make predictions and improve their performance as time goes on. In addition, machine learning algorithms are broadly categorized into three types. These are, supervised learning which involves training a model on labeled data, where the desired output is known. In this context, model learns to map inputs to outputs based on the provided instance. Secondly, unsupervised learning that works with unlabeled data and aims to find hidden patterns or intrinsic structures in the input data and finally, reinforcement learning which involves training agents to make a sequence of decisions by rewarding them for good actions and penalizing them for bad ones. The imperativeness of each of the types is that they have subs that facilitate their operations. For instance, supervised learning is further divided into: classification, and regression, while unsupervised learning has to its kitty, clustering, dimensionality reduction and association whereas, reinforcement learning subs includes, model-free methods, model-based methods and value-based methods (Geeks-For-Geeks, 2024)

Machine learning algorithms therefore, are necessary tools for analyzing data, making predictions, and uncovering insights that drive decision-making and innovation in various fields including library and information science. The emphasis being that machine learning algorithms improve in their performance over time as they are trained and exposed to more data. Machine learning models so to speak, are the output or what the program learns from running an algorithm on training data. This implies that the more data used, the better the model will get.

Some most notable and popular machine learning algorithms in use as highlighted include: linear regression which models the relationship between dependent and independent variables using a linear approach, logistic regression used in modeling the probability of a binary outcome by utilizing a logistic function, support vector machines (SVM) that locates the hyper plane that best separates different classes by maximizing the margin between them, k-Nearest Neighbors (k-NN) that classifies instances

based on the majority class among the k-nearest neighbors in the feature space as well as decision trees that splits data into subsets based on the value of input features, creating a tree-like model of decisions. Others are, random forest which is ensembles of decision trees that improves accuracy and controls over-fitting by averaging multiple trees trained on different subsets of data, naive Bayes that uses Bayes' theorem with the assumption of feature independence to classify instances, Principal Component Analysis (PCA) that reduces the dimensionality of data by transforming it to a new set of orthogonal features that capture the maximum variance and Apriori algorithm which identifies frequent itemsets in transactional data and generates association rules as well as k-Means clustering that partitions data into k clusters based on feature similarity (Geeks-For-Geeks, 2024)

3.2. AREAS MACHINE LEARNING COULD BE ADOPTED IN LIBRARY SERVICES

Machine learning as the offshoot of AI is as important to the library as the AI is generally. The implication is that machine learning has the potential to reasonably transform library operations and services, making them more efficient, user-friendly and focused to the needs of users. As highlighted by Library Academy there are many areas that machine learning can be deployed in the library. These areas as underscored include, cataloging and classification, in that in automated metadata generation, ML algorithms can be employed to analyze content and generate metadata, making the cataloging process faster and more accurate. Above all, in automated classification, ML models can learn to classify materials based on their content, allowing for improved organization and search capabilities. It has also been found, to be a veritable tool in information retrieval. As revealed, relevant books, articles or other resources based on user preferences, borrowing history and behavior patterns can be easily suggested using AI powered recommendation systems, besides, by understanding the context and meaning behind queries, improving the accuracy and relevance of search results ML algorithms can enhance search engines (Library Academy, 2024).

ML has also be found useful in providing user services. The underscore, is that AI-driven chatbot can assist users with general inquiries, guide them through library resources and provide real-time support and it can also be of help, in creating personalized learning paths for users, recommending resources and activities based on their individual needs and learning styles. ML can also enhance collection development under predictive Analytics, as ML algorithms can analyze usage patterns, circulation data, and user feedback to predict future demand for specific materials thereby aiding in collection development decisions.

Under preservation and conservation, ML as noted can be of support in digitization planning in that ML algorithms can assist in prioritizing materials for digitization based on factors such as historical significance, demand and preservation needs. ML has also been found to be a veritable tool for data management and analysis as it can be used for fraud detection. In other words, ML algorithms can assist in identifying fraudulent activities, such as unauthorized access or misuse of library resources (Library Academy, 2024).

Available evidence based on researches have revealed also other areas that ML could be deployed in library settings. According to research, recommender systems (RSs) which are software tools and techniques that generate meaningful recommendations to the users based on their preference for items and products could be utilized in providing a personalized experience to library patrons through filtering, rating, preference or options that might interest them as output (Das and Islam, 2021). As has been noted, RSs are becoming popular tools for evaluating and filtering large amounts of information too. With a view to improving library services and providing personalized services to the users. Evidence shows that different kinds of such recommendation algorithms have been widely used by the libraries (Xiao and Gao, 2020). A case in point is that a group of researchers who utilized 2,293,642 loan records from 44,571 users of a university library using two machine learning techniques; SVM and association rules to recommend books to both undergraduate and graduate students of various faculties. SVM was used according to, the confidence from an association rule, likenesses between titles, match/mismatches between categories, and similarities between the outlines in the book databases (Tsuji, Takizawa, Sato, et. al, 2014). Another study, delved into Bayes estimator to offer generalized recommendations based on the item's popularity score. Hence, the outcome shows that popular books have a greater probability of being chosen by other readers (Xiao and Gao, 2020). Walker and Jiang (2019), employed logistic regression and Ada-Boost to investigate the viability of machine learning as a platform for predictive modelling of demand-driven acquisition, (DDA) and purchasing of e-books. The logistic regression analysis was performed by general linear model (glm) R function and the Ada-Boost was powered by the Ada-Bag R package. Concerning the implementation of real-time virtual reference service by a newly developed smart talking robot called Xiaotu, Yao et al. (2011), adopted self-directed learning techniques. Furthermore, Short (2019), experimented with text mining, classification, clustering and topic-modelling focusing on 5 years-subject analysis of a novel to enhance the experience of cataloguing and subject analysis. Natural language processing (NLP), a branch of AI, was also employed in this study to understand the Chinese natural language talking function through natural language communication between respondent and robot. Another sophisticated AI technique, pattern recognition was investigated by Yang, He, et al., (2015). This study focused on book inventory management of a library and the retrieval system based on scene text reading. They proposed a design text recognition model utilizing rich supervision. While Lei et al (2018), proposed a convolutional-neural-network-based book label recognition approach for digging out the misplaced books. The authors emphasized on image processing techniques and convolutional neural networks (CNNs) to excerpt the label's characters attached to each book from the images of the bookshelves and to train a classifier for recognizing characters respectively. In another study, Du, Lim and Tan (2019), emphasized on library security through passive RFID tags based on pattern recognition through collection and analysis of profiling distribution, reading activity, reader's trajectory, and thus identification of picked up and misplaced books.

Generally, machine learning could be used for collection building and management, processing in libraries, circulation and user studies, reference service, library administration, library customization and retrieval, research and scholarship, service quality and innovation, intelligent agents for information search and retrieval, study on implementation and existing technologies and solution. As explained. As

revealed by Massis (2018) and Cox, Andrew, Pinfield and Rutter (2019), using ML, it is possible to discover, search and analyze any vast library collections. It brings the skills and knowledge of library staff, scholars and students together to design an intelligent information system that respects the sources, engages critical inquiry, fosters imagination and supports human learning and knowledge creation. In the process, the service innovations will double the result as it will cut the effort half for the intelligent library's development and will be the most important development direction of the intelligent library (Chen and Shen, 2019). In addition, the services provided by the intelligent library have a great impact on the frequency of using the resources of the library for readers. Significantly library used data would feed into learning analytic with which, data that libraries hold on user activity and the way they use services will contribute more widely to their kind of learning journey in the future (Cox, Andrew, Pinfield and Rutter, 2019)

Some major activities for many libraries include; acquisition, processing, collection building and management. Machine learning as revealed, helps with potential intelligent roles like, data acquisition, data curation and data quality control (Gul, and Bano, 2019). It has also been posited that, ML can be utilized in cataloguing, classification, acquisition of collections, indexing and management activities as well (Wójcik, 2020; Omehia, 2020).

One other important area machine learning could be used, is in the area of generating metadata and resource discovery. As stated, machine learning can be used in libraries for metadata generation, resource discovery and rich full-text identification and extraction (Cox, Andrew, Pinfield and Rutter, 2019) In addition, machine learning is used to generate subject headings, for instance, metadata directly describing the resource (a bibliographic record) and supplemental metadata about the author or subjects (Boman, 2019). Different intelligent technologies are also used for improving better library operations and services through ML technology, such as intelligent shelves. Intelligent shelf is capable of reading books on the shelves, although the shelf itself cannot tell the specific location for a book. However, an intelligent browsing table in the library, which is able to collect information about users' reading habits, such information, can be used in the arrangement of collections and shelves (Rubin, Chen and Thorimbert, 2010).

Another important aspect of library services focuses on reference services and here also ML can play major roles. An artificially intelligent conversational agent or chatbot might works as a virtual reference librarian which will enhance face-to-face human interaction and also act as library web site tour guides, automated virtual reference and readers' advisory librarians, and virtual story-tellers (Xiao and Gao, 2020; Gul and Bano, 2019; Rubin, Chen and Thorimbert, 2010). Some highlighted samples of virtual/dynamic reference services include; 'the Stanford Encyclopaedia of Philosophy project' in which an expert team offers dynamic reference services, 'Virtual Reference Desk' in which reference agents deliver digital reference services and an agent-based system that supports access to information from the repositories in the web (Allen, Nodelman, and Zalta, 2002).

Another principle area ML implementation is necessary as noted, is in the area of information search and retrieval. As opined by Liu (2011), agent technology such as strategic search support, proactive

support for query formulation, intelligent assistance to information search and retrieval and personalized services to users has been used to support the information search process in digital libraries (DLs). An agent based architecture supports high-level search activity in federated DLs combining the advantages of previous approaches. Depending on the interest of the user, intelligent software agents search of the DLs can return the information which the user is looking for and also through the personal agents, users can customize their interfaces. Therefore, as underscored by Wójcik (2020), librarians now tend to use artificially intelligent solutions for advancing the better, quicker and efficient process of acquisition, processing and analysis of information to meet information needs of users. According to Fox (2016) and Omehia (2020), ML could also shape the library operations and services with the focus on the library's basic operations, administrations, research, scholarship, service innovation, usability, retrieval and so on, deep learning, neural network algorithms as well as convolutional neural networks have also been proved as powerful tools for scholarship and research reported the studies.

There have also been several studies found that have investigated the behavior of users towards machine-enabled and intelligent library. Going down the memory lane, Nardi and O'Day (1996), seem to be the first to introduce the concept of an intelligent reference librarian for user service through the application of artificial agent in libraries. As indicated, user modelling in digital libraries is also being done through machine learning by following the process of data preprocessing, pattern discovery and validation (Frias-Martinez, et al, 2006; Zuccala, et al, 2007). Other areas found that ML technologies can proffer solutions in Libraries thereby supporting a variety of library operations include; reader rating, resource discovery, delivery and preservation through the use of recommender systems, linked data, expert systems, robots among others (Arlitsch and Newell, 2017; Xiao and Gao, 2020; Asemi, Ko and Nowkarizi, 2020; Schreur, 2020).

3.3. BENEFITS OF ADOPTING MACHINE LEARNING IN LIBRARIES

ML as a subset of AI is recorded to be of great benefits to all organizations regardless of shapes and sizes which libraries are part, with new possibilities coming up on daily basis. Worthy of note is that, as the amount of data grow in size and complexity, automated and intelligent systems are becoming vital to helping institutions as well as organizations automate tasks, unlock value and generate actionable insights to achieve better outcomes. The growing body of research and literature underscores machine learning fundamental significance in the digital ecosystem for both librarians and libraries. Some of the highlighted benefits of employing ML in library services as have been noted include inter-alia is that with machine learning, a wider range of unstructured and structured data sources can be analyzed and activated, decision-making is made faster which in turn, improves data integrity, accelerates data processing and reduces human error for more informed decision-making. Furthermore, Its adoption in the library will result to increment in operational efficiency and reduction in costs and also empowers employees by integrating predictive analytics and insights into business reporting and applications (Coursera, 2025).

The introduction of machine learning into library services will pave way for the automation of repetitive or manual processes that will help drive informed decision-making. The aversion is that companies across industries are using ML in various ways to transform how they work and do business. Incorporating ML capabilities into their strategies and systems has helped organizations rethink how they use their data and available resources, drive productivity and efficiency, enhance data-driven decision-making through predictive analytics and improve customer and employee experiences (Coursera, 2025). In this regard, libraries presumably are better for it.

As has been buttressed, ML techniques could be useful for resource discovery in that, the web crawlers and other data harvesting tools can be applied for automation and advanced classifications of information resources to redefine the resource accessibility of library users. Data mining techniques can also be used to harvest data from both homogenous and heterogeneous systems for understanding the library usages patterns (Mitchell, 2006).

ML has also been indicated to be a useful tool to enhancing library security, user identification and book title recognition. As stated by Das and Islam (2021), some advanced ML techniques like pattern recognition and MAS are also being used to ensuring library security; user identification, book title recognition as well as RFID management and other administration activities. In addition, deep learning, neural network algorithms and convolutional neural networks, all aspect of ML, have also been proved as powerful tools for scholarship, collections discovery, search and analysis.

Using ML in library operations will also decrease operational costs. The assertion is that machine learning may help businesses to automate some of its jobs, causing overall operational costs to decrease. It will as well improve operational efficiency and accuracy. This is because, machine learning models are able to perform certain narrow tasks with extreme efficiency and accuracy, ensuring that some tasks are completed to a high degree in a timely manner.

Another gain of adopting ML in library services is its ability to improved insights. The explanation is that machine learning has the potential to quickly identify trends and patterns in large amounts of data that would be time consuming for humans. These insights can equip researchers and society as a whole with new knowledge that has the potential to help them achieve their overall goals. It is further expressed that machine learning (ML) has the potential to significantly transform library operations and services, making them more efficient, user-friendly and tailored to the needs of library users (Library Academy, 2024).

It has also been posited that ML has been transforming various tasks and fields especially in Management Information System (MIS) with its implementation using various techniques, such as rule-based systems and expert systems. The source revealed that it has impacted MIS in the areas of data quality which is used to analyze data and identify inconsistencies, errors and missing data thereby helping organizations to improve their data quality and ensuring that the data used in MIS is accurate and complete. As noted as a case in point, is that of Natural Language Processing (NLP) algorithms that has the ability to analyze and clean up unstructured data, such as social media posts or customer feedback. If ML can automatically categorize and filter data, ML can also be of assistance to libraries

in identifying patterns and trends that would be difficult to spot manually, enabling them to make data-driven decisions more efficiently and accurately (Encora Digital, 2025).

ML has also been found to be a functional tool for maintaining data security. ML apparently, can be used to detect and respond to security threats, including unauthorized access and data breaches. This can assist libraries in the area of improving their data security and protecting sensitive information. ML can also be used to analyze user behavior and identify anomalies that may indicate fraudulent or malicious activity. For example, let's take a case whereby an employee hack into the library's network from an unfamiliar location and attempts to access sensitive data, ML algorithms can flag the activity as suspicious and prompt additional authentication checks or block access based on the dataset studied (Encora Digital, 2025).

ML is also seen as an essential tool for data sharing. As noted, it can be used to integrate multiple systems and applications, enabling data to be shared more easily and efficiently. This can help libraries to streamline their operations and improve collaboration. For instance, the library could use an AI-powered Chatbot that can integrate with all different MIS applications. The Chatbot could use NLP to understand user queries and retrieve relevant data from the different applications. A circulation librarian, could ask the Chabot for a user's borrowing history and the Chatbot could retrieve that information from the user data and request form.

ML has also been identified as a working tool for data capturing. As explained, by using ML, the data collection and analysis process can be automated, reducing the need for manual intervention and improving the speed and accuracy of the analysis. For instance, machine learning algorithms can be used to automatically classify and categorize data, identify patterns and anomalies and generate reports in real-time. This can assist libraries to scale their MIS systems without adding additional staff or increasing the workload on existing staff (Geeks-For-Geeks, 2024).

Being part of the AI family, ML is as well perceived as an effective tool for Data Analysis. This is on the ground that an AI-powered predictive analytics can help libraries make more accurate and data-driven decisions, improving the efficiency and effectiveness of their LMIS systems. Generally, the integrating ML into library services has the potential for significantly enhancing user engagement (Library Academy, 2024).

Finally, machine learning provides an array of possible tools to help libraries generate metadata for digital resources, allowing cataloguing to not only increase the speed of metadata generation but also vastly improve the depth and breadth of subject terms (Vijayakumar and Sheshadri, 2019).

3.4. CONSTRAINTS IN ADOPTING MACHINE LEARNING IN LIBRARIES

To every coin, there are two sides, same applies to every invented technology as there are always two sides to it, which are the gains and the associated dangers of adoption. In the case of ML, the story is not different as there are notable dangers in the use of the technology regardless of the numerous

identified benefits. Though it has been noted that machine learning brings increment in operational efficiency and reduction in costs and also empowers employees by integrating predictive analytics and insights into business reporting and applications, but the aversion is that there is this challenge of job loss or layoff as with the introduction of ML in the library as some jobs are automated, workers in the affected area will likely be faced with challenge of loss of jobs, which could force them into switching over to new career or risk long-term unemployment (Johnson, 2020) .

There is also the danger of lack of human elements. No matter how it is looked at, models that are tasked with doing a very narrow task may also miss many of the “human” aspects of the job that are important to it but potentially overlooked by developers. There is further the challenge of ingrained biases. In life, man is known to be fallible and subject to bias likewise machine invented by man. The explicit is that just like the humans that create them, machine learning models are bound to exhibit bias due to the occasionally changing of data sets that they are trained on. Furtherance, there are other identified notable challenges associated with the use of ML in libraries. This inter-alia includes, the need for large amounts of quality data, the potential for bias in AI algorithms and the need for specialized skills to implement and maintain ML systems (Greenstein, 2022; Nah, Zheng, Cai, Siau and Chen, 2023).

One other primary challenge libraries in Nigeria are likely to have in adopting ML, is the need for robust technological infrastructure. As stated by Onwubiko 2025), one of the key challenge that has bedeviled libraries in Nigeria in adopting most emerging technologies in information and communication is non-existence of robust technological infrastructure.

Inasmuch as ML hold the promise of expanding access to information, the argument is that, adopting ML raises concerns about the digital inclusion and accessibility as not every individual has access to the required electronic devices or reliable internet connectivity to participate fully in a digital library experience. The belief, is that this digital divide may in a very high extent affect communities that are digitally sidetracked, thereby widening the existing gap in inequality in access to information and by extension education. A situation that negates UN-SDGs 4 which talks about equality in education (United Nations, 2015). This situation calls for libraries offering both physical and digital library services as a way forward.

Another challenge libraries may face in adopting ML is that of curation and quality of the digital content. Ensuring that virtual collections are accurate, reliable and ubiquitous is a sine-qua-non to maintaining the integrity of any library services. When one recalls that copyright and intellectual property conundrum are more pronounced in the digital ecosystem, it behooves libraries, to come up with clear guidelines on how to acquire, use and disseminate digital or virtual content. In this regard, for libraries to worth their onus and maintain their integrity as information hub and driving access to contemporary technologies, they must strike a balance between providing individualized services and protecting user privacy as a way of surmounting ethical conundrum (Onwubiko, 2025).

4. DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Based on the outcome of the review which expresses the thought, assertions and discoveries of researchers on the topic under study, it was identified that there are needs for libraries to adopt ML technology to enhance their services. As noted, ML can be employed in cataloging and classification as ML models can learn to classify materials based on their content, allowing for improved organization and search capabilities as well as information retrieval where ML algorithms can enhance search engines by understanding the context and meaning behind queries, improving the accuracy and relevance of search results (Library Academy, 2024). The other areas ML can be adopted in library services as asserted are in the enhancement of search engines, collection development under predictive Analytics and data management and analysis as well as in users services, personalized services with aid of recommender systems (RSs) and information search and retrieval among others (Walker and Jiang, 2019; Cox, et al., 2019; Wójcik, 2020; Omehia, 2020).

It was also found through the systematic review of literature that there are many accrued benefits of adopting ML in libraries. As revealed, with ML, a wider range of unstructured and structured data sources can be analyzed and activated, decision-making are faster thereby improving data integrity, accelerating data processing and reducing human error for more informed and this facilitates faster decision-making. It further brings increment in operational efficiency and reduction in costs and also empowers employees by integrating predictive analytics and insights into business reporting and applications (Coursera, 2025). Other works that highlighted the gains of utilizing ML in library services though not all inclusive include; Walker & Jiang, 2019; Short, 2019, Das and Islam, 2021, Library Academy, 2024 and Encora Digital, 2025.

Since every coin has two sides, there are also some exposed dangers associated with the adoption of ML in libraries. Some of the constraints as identified, include; fear of layoff of impacted workers, ingrained biases, danger of lack of human elements, the need for large amounts of quality data, the potential for bias in ML algorithms and the need for specialized skills to implement and maintain ML systems, need for robust technological infrastructure and the concerns about the digital inclusion and accessibility (Coursera, 2025; Onwubiko, 2025).

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Ultimately, every change comes with its own peculiar challenge(s) and the adoption of ML in libraries should therefore not be seen by librarians in this part of the globe as an exception. From the review, the gains of adopting ML in libraries far outweighs the associated dangers or fears. In this regard, one can deduce that adopting ML into library operations is rather more gainful than the associated conundrums. Against this backdrop, to cope with the emerging technology, librarians need to change their roles and promote the transformation of library operations and services assisted with machine

learning and work towards understanding the phenomena and creating innovation in this field. Inasmuch as there are notable challenges such as the need for large amounts of quality data, the potential for bias in ML algorithms and the need for specialized skills to implement and maintain ML systems. The bottom line is that, the impact of ML as an offshoot of AI on library services as recorded, is significant and will continue to transform the way organizations make decisions. In which case, librarians as drivers of digital literacy would not like to be left behind. As a matter of fact, machine learning algorithms have been found to be essential tools for analyzing data, making predictions and uncovering insights that drive decision-making and innovation in various fields. Against this backdrop the following suggestions are made:

- I. It is not in doubt that the bulk of making the application of ML succeed in academic libraries falls on the table of the librarians. That being the case, librarians needs to be trained and retrained on the intricacies of the art of utilizing ML in the library and should master the art that will lead to its optimal use in the provision of library services. They should also in-turn, train the users on how to leverage the technology for effective service delivery and harnessing of the benefits of the technology in a digital ecosystem. This implies that libraries and librarians should carryout intensive ML-literacy campaign.
- II. In line with the fifth revolution (5IR) whose aims are to create a more inclusive, equitable, and sustainable future by addressing social, environmental and economic challenges through ethical and human-centered technological solutions, those developing and designing avatars, should see it, as social responsibility and promotion of human equality to ensure that tools for the creation of ML are inclusive and put into consideration the dignity of all users, regardless of cognitive and physical abilities as well as gender and race. In the contrary, projects the promotion of stereotypes and enhancement of all already established existing inequalities within the digital ecosystem which is being fight against by international organization like UNESCO and WHO. Suffice to say that the accessibility of ML by all users should not be in doubt as the designers are expected to incorporate abilities and communication styles that will ensure that all users can easily be involved in digital communities.
- III. While there is need to leverage the creative and transformative importance of ML, consideration should be given to balancing the approach with regards to upholding the ethical principles safeguarding users' rights. This is to say, that users privacy, the principle of inclusivity as preached and enshrined in one of UN-SDGs and authenticity of online interactions should be first on the list.
- IV. Libraries should be equipped with robust and state of the art technological infrastructure to ensure optimal operations of ML when it comes on stream as part of library tools.
- V. Libraries should clear the allayed fear of the needed human elements and specialized skills to implement and maintain ML systems by training the librarians beforehand ensuring that all

needed skills are acquired by the staff before the full integration of the technology into the library operations.

- VI. As a follow up to the above, resolving the moral dilemma associated with job loss inasmuch as it requires strong policy frameworks and regulatory actions that call for governments, industry stakeholders, and academia to work together to create policies like re-skilling programs, tests with universal basic income, and ethical criteria for ML deployment, a well-trained librarians with perfect ML skills need fear no fall. So the advice to librarians in Nigeria is that they should embark on self-sponsored training, retraining and retraining as there are many online courses now on AI and machine learning (ML) that are beneficiary to librarians.
- VII. In the issue of ML having the potential for bias in ML algorithms, the monitoring bodies should ensure that developers and designers of ML tools in-built into the system, means of inhibiting biasness by the ML algorithms. Besides, to subdue the menace of data bias and promote fairness considering the fact that ML systems are trained on data and where the training data is biased or reflects societal prejudices, the ML models has the tendency to perpetuate those biases. To this end, librarians need to carefully curate and preprocess data to ensure fairness and mitigate bias in ML models. Librarians should aim for reproducibility by providing clear documentation of their ML models, algorithms, and datasets. It is crucial to ensure that ML models are robust and can generalize well to unseen data, avoiding over fitting or biased results.

REFERENCES

- Abhay, K. B and Dhanya, J (2016). Big data: challenges opportunities and realities, Effective big data management and opportunities for implementation, pp. 1-24
- Ahmed, A., Suprateek, S and Roger HL Chiang (2016), Big data research in information systems: Toward an inclusive research agenda, Journal of the association for information systems, Vol. 17, No.2, pp. 3.
- Allen, C., Nodelman, U and Zalta, E. N. (2002). The Stanford encyclopedia of philosophy a developed dynamic reference work. *Metaphilosophy*, Vol.33, No.1–2, pp. 210–228. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-9973.00225>
- Arlitsch, K., & Newell, B. (2017). Thriving in the Age of Accelerations: A Brief Look at the Societal Effects of Artificial Intelligence and the 13 Opportunities for Libraries. *Journal of Library Administration*, Vol. 57No.7, pp. 789–798. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01930826.2017.1362912>
- Asemi, A., Ko, A and Nowkarizi, M. (2020). Intelligent libraries: a review on expert systems, artificial intelligence, and robot. *Library Hi Tech*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/LHT02-2020-0038>
- Ayyadevara, V. K. (2018). *Pro Machine Learning Algorithms : A Hands-On Approach to Implementing Algorithms in Python and R*. A press.
- Boman, C. (2019). Chapter 4. An Exploration of Machine Learning in Libraries. *Library Technology Reports*, Vol.55, No.1, p.21. <https://search.proquest.com/docview/2161880267?accountid=11862>
- Coursera (2025). What Is Machine Learning? Definition, Types, and Examples. <https://www.coursera.org/articles/what-is-machine-learning?msocid=32282ca20c67648e-e29eb393c0d7a65b>

Chen, M., & Shen, C.-W. (2019). The correlation analysis between the service quality of intelligent library and the behavioral intention of users. *Electronic Library*, Vol. 38, No. 1, pp. 95–112. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EL-07-2019-0163>

Cox, Andrew M., Pinfield, S and Rutter, S. (2019). The intelligent library: Thought leaders' views on the likely impact of artificial intelligence on academic libraries. *Library Hi Tech*, vol. 37, No. 3, pp. 418–435. <https://doi.org/10.1108/LHT-08-2018-0105>

Das, R.K and Islam, M.S (2021). Application of Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning in Libraries: A Systematic Review. <https://www.academia.edu/82294365/application-of-artificial-intelligence-and-machine-learning-in-libraries-a-systematic-review>

Du, Y., Lim, Y and Tan, Y. (2019). Activity recognition using RFID phase profiling in smart library. *IEICE Transactions on Information and Systems*, E102D Vol. 4, pp. 768–776. <https://doi.org/10.1587/transinf.2018DAP0010>

Encora Digital (2025). AI & Machine Learning in Management Information Systems <https://insights.encora.com/insights/artificial-intelligence-machine-learning-implication-on-management-information-system>

Ex Libris Whitepaper (2020) Artificial Intelligence in the Library: Advantages, Challenges and Tradition. [Ex Libris Artificial Intelligence White Paper 1 .pdf - Artificial Intelligence in the Library: Advantages Challenges and Tradition An Ex Libris | Course Hero](#)

Fernandez, P. (2016). “Through the looking glass: envisioning new library technologies” how artificial intelligence will impact libraries. *Library Hi Tech News*, Vol. 33, No. 5, pp. 5–8. <https://doi.org/10.1108/LHTN-05-2016-0024>

Fox, R. (2016). Digital libraries: the systems analysis perspective machine erudition. *Digital Library Perspectives*, Vol. 32, No. 2, pp. 62–67. <https://doi.org/10.1108/DLP-02-2016-0006>

Frias-Martinez, E., Magoulas, G., Chen, S., & Macredie, R. (2006). Automated user modeling for personalized digital libraries. *International Journal of Information Management*, Vol. 26, No. 3, pp. 234–248. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2006.02.006>

Geeks-For-Geeks (2024). Machine learning algorithms <https://www.geeksforgeeks.org/machine-learning-algorithms>

Google Cloud (2024). Artificial intelligence versus machine learning <https://cloud.google.com/learn/artificial-intelligence-vs-machine-learning>

Gul, S.and Bano, S. (2019). Smart libraries: an emerging and innovative technological habitat of 21st century. *Electronic Library*, Vol. 7, No. 5, pp. 764–783. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EL-02-2019-0052>

IBM (2021). "What is Machine Learning?" <https://www.ibm.com/topics/machine-learning>

Greenstein, B. (2022, April, 20) AiThORITY: Interview with Bret Greenstein, Partner, Cloud & Digital – Analytics Insights at PwC. <https://aithority.com/technology/analytics/aithority-interview-with-bret-greenstein-partner-cloud-digital-analytics-insights-at-pwc/#>

Johnson, L., Adams, B, S., Estrada, V and Freeman, A. (2015). NMC Horizon Report: Higher Education Edition. Austin, Texas: The New Media Consortium

Lei, L., Tang, J and Wang, Z. (2018). Book title recognition for smart library with deep learning. <https://doi.org/10.1117/12.2312245>

Library Academy (2024). Application of Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning in Library Operations and Services <https://libraryscience.in/2024/01/artificial-intelligence-and-machine-learning-in-library.html>

Liu, G. (2011). The application of intelligent agents in libraries: a survey. *Program*, 45(1), 78–97. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/00330330331111107411>

- Massis, B. (2018). Artificial intelligence arrives in the library. *Information and Learning Science*, Vol. 119, No. 7/8, pp. 456–459. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/ILS-02-2018-0011>
- Mitchell, S. (2006). Machine Assistance in Collection Building: New Tools, Research, Issues, and Reflections. *Information Technology and Libraries*, Vol. 25, No. 4, pp. 190–216. <https://search.proquest.com/docview/215829908?accountid=11862>
- Mohamed, A., Ali, C., Fakhri, Y and Noreddine, G. (2022), "A survey on the challenges of data integration", 2022 9th International Conference on Wireless Networks and Mobile Communications (*WINCOM*), pp. 1-6.
- Muhammad N., Tauseef, J., Diaz-Martinez, S. B., Montesano, N., Muhammad I.T., et al., (2022). Trends and future perspective challenges in big data, *Advances in Intelligent Data Analysis and Applications: Proceeding of the Sixth Euro-China Conference on Intelligent Data Analysis and Applications*, pp. 309-325.
- Nah, F. F.-H., Zheng, R., Cai, J., Siau, K and Chen, L. (2023). Generative AI and ChatGPT: Applications, challenges and AI-human collaboration. *Journal of Information Technology Case and Application Research*, Vol. 25, No. 3, pp. 277–304. DOI: 10.1080/15228053.2023.2233814
- Nardi, B. A., & O'Day, V. (1996). Intelligent agents: What we learned at the library. *Libri*, 46(2), 59–88. <https://doi.org/10.1515/libr.1996.46.2.59>
- Omehia, A. (2020). Pros and Cons of Artificial Intelligence in 21st Century Library and Information 16 Service Delivery. Vol. 13, pp. 220– 227.
- Onwubiko, E.C (2025). The Double-Edged Sword of Artificial Intelligence in Academic Libraries and Research. *Graduate Journal of Interdisciplinary Research, Reports and Reviews*, Vol.3, No. 01, pp. 1-15. Retrieved from <https://jpr.vyomhansjournals.com/index.php/gjir/article/view/33>
- Rubin, V. L., Chen, Y., and Thorimbert, L. M. (2010). Artificially intelligent conversational agents in libraries. *Library Hi Tech*, Vol. 28, No. 4, pp. 496–522. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/07378831011096196>
- Schreur, P. E. (2020). The Use of Linked Data and Artificial Intelligence as Key Elements in the Transformation of Technical Services. *Cataloging and Classification Quarterly*, Vol. 58, No. 5, pp. 473–485. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01639374.2020.1772434>
- Short, M. (2019). Text Mining and Subject Analysis for Fiction; or, Using Machine Learning and Information Extraction to Assign Subject Headings to Dime Novels. *Cataloging and Classification Quarterly*, Vol. 57, No. 5, pp. 315–336. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01639374.2019.1653413>
- United Nations (2015). The 17 goals | Sustainable Development. <https://sdgs.un.org/goals>
- Vijayakumar¹, S and Sheshadri, K.N (2019). Applications of Artificial Intelligence in Academic Libraries. *International Journal of Computer Sciences and Engineering*, Vol. 7, No. 16, pp. 136-140. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-78582-8_23
- Walker, K. W and Jiang, Z. (2019). Application of adaptive boosting (AdaBoost) in demand-driven acquisition (DDA) prediction: A machine-learning approach. *Journal of Academic Librarianship*, Vol. 45, No. 3, pp. 203–212. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acalib.2019.02.013>
- Wiederhold, G., JMcCarthy, J and Feigenbaum, E (1990). "[Memorial Resolution: Arthur L. Samuel](#)" (PDF). [Stanford University](#) Historical Society. Archived from [the original](#) (PDF) on 26 May 2011.
- Wójcik, M. (2020). Augmented intelligence technology. The ethical and practical problems of its implementation in libraries. *Library Hi Tech*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/LHT-02-2020-0043>
- Xiao, J and Gao, W. (2020). Connecting the Dots: Reader Ratings, Bibliographic Data, and Machine Learning Algorithms for Monograph Selection. *Serials Librarian*, Vol. 78, No. 1–4, pp. 117–122. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0361526X.2020.1707599>

Yang, X., He, D., Huang, W., Ororbia, A., Yao, F., Zhang, C and Chen, W. (2015). Smart talking robot Xiaotu: participatory library service based on artificial intelligence. *Library Hi Tech*, Vol. 33, No. 2, pp. 245–260. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/LHT-02-2015-0010>

Zuccala, A., Thelwall, M., Oppenheim, C and Dhiensa, R. (2007). Web intelligence analyses of digital libraries: A case study of the National electronic Library for Health (NeLH). *Journal of Documentation*, Vol. 63, No. 4, pp. 558–589. <https://doi.org/10.1108/00220410710759011>